

**PROJECT EL AR: A PEDAGOGICAL APPROACH FOR SELECTED
NON-READER LEARNERS OF GRADE 3 AT LR SEBASTIAN
ELEMENTARY SCHOOL**

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 27

Issue 4

Pages: 388-391

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2568

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14018661

Manuscript Accepted: 10-01-2024

Project EL AR: A Pedagogical Approach for Selected Non-Reader Learners of Grade 3 at LR Sebastian Elementary School

Jasmin Dumamba-Salilama*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The Project Enhancing Learners Abilities in Reading (EL AR), a pedagogical approach, serves as an intervention designed to support selected Grade 3 pupils who have experienced significant cognitive challenges due to the COVID-19 pandemic. This is an innovative approach aimed at enhancing the reading abilities of selected non-readers. By focusing on the development of fundamental skills, including phonological awareness, decoding, word recognition, fluency, and listening comprehension, the strategies employed are grounded in evidence-based teaching methods known to be effective in fostering literacy skills. The research follows a mixed-methods approach, involving both quantitative and qualitative data collection methods. The participants include a sample of grade 3 learners who are non-readers at LR Sebastian Elementary School. The intervention involves implementing Project EL AR, which incorporates innovative teaching strategies, interactive reading materials, and personalized learning approaches. BoSY- and MoSY-intervention assessments, surveys, interviews, and observations were conducted to collect data. The data were analyzed using statistical methods for quantitative data and thematic analysis for qualitative data. The results of this study will provide insights into the impact of Project EL AR on the literacy development of non-readers in grade 3, offering valuable implications for educators, policymakers, and future research in addressing the issue of non-readers. The project's primary aim is to enhance the reading competencies of these learners, enabling them to achieve literacy levels commensurate with their grade level.

Keywords: *Project EL AR, reading intervention, non-readers, cognitive challenges, literacy development*

Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic had a major impact on the world, and its effects have been felt in the education system as well. Many students, particularly those in primary grades, have been unable to attend school for extended periods due to closures and other safety protocols. As a result, many of these students have experienced a severe decline in their reading skills. To combat this issue, the Ministry of Basic Higher and Technical Education (MBHTE) developed the 5 Bs (Bawat Bata sa Bangsamoro Bumabasa at Bumibilang) program, and the Schools Division of Cotabato City (SDOCC) executed Regional Memorandum No. 558, s. 2023, entitled Implementation of the End-of-School Year (EOSY) Reading Program to address the literacy gaps and help bolster students' literacy skills.

The program served as a springboard for the Regional Reading Program during the SY 2021-2022 school break, which lasted three to five weeks, from July 24 to August 25, 2023. The target learners are all incoming Grades 1-12 students who have been identified as full refreshers, moderate refreshers, or light refreshers based on EoSY CRLA and Phil IRI results.

EoSY reading programs have several potential benefits for students in the primary grades. These programs can help address the issue of declining literacy skills caused by the pandemic. By providing students with additional opportunities to read, the programs can also help to reverse the negative effects of the pandemic and ensure that students remain on track with their literacy development. Yet the beginning of the school year reading assessment results suggest that some of the Grade 3 pupils still lack the necessary skills for reading.

Based on the BoSY reading assessment result for S.Y. 2023-2024, 66 out of 262 Grade 3 pupils in LR Sebastian Elementary School are under the Full Refresher level. With this, there is a need to improve pupils' reading abilities. Thus, the researcher is motivated to help Grade 3 pupils improve their reading ability through Project EL AR (Enhancing Learners Ability in Reading).

One of the key components of this project is focusing on the development of fundamental skills, including phonological awareness, decoding, word recognition, fluency, and listening comprehension, which are fundamental building blocks of reading. The Project EL AR approach also promotes active learning and engagement through reading, reciting, and reviewing, thereby helping students to better understand and retain the phonics and words they are learning.

In the long run, the implementation of Project EL AR could contribute to the overall improvement of the quality of education at LRSES as well as to the personal and academic growth of the learners it targets. This project underscores the importance of innovative teaching methods for addressing learning challenges and enhancing the learning experience for all learners.

Research Questions

This action research aimed to determine the effectiveness of the Project EL AR approach for selected non-reader learners of Grade 3 at LR Sebastian Elementary School. Specifically, it sought to answer the following sub-questions:

1. How effective is Project EL AR as a pedagogical approach for improving the reading abilities of selected non-reader learners in Grade 3 at LR Sebastian Elementary School?
2. What are the observable changes in the learning behavior of Grade 3 non-reader learners at LR Sebastian Elementary School following the application of the Project EL AR pedagogical approach?
3. To what extent does Project EL AR improve the overall academic performance of selected non-reader learners in Grade 3 at LR Sebastian Elementary School year 2023-2024?

Literature Review

Reading success is crucial to academic success. Reading difficulties on the other hand hamper every aspect of a child's academic accomplishment. Thus, early reading is critical. Early reading instruction helps children develop superior reading skills and achieve greater academic success. When children fall behind in reading, they will struggle in other subjects and with schooling. They feel frustrated, lose motivation, and fall further behind, creating a downward spiral (Quimbo, 2021).

In this research, the researcher determines how effective Project EL AR is as a pedagogical intervention that will help grade three learners who have become non-readers because of the COVID-19 pandemic and improve their reading skills. The intervention is built on well-founded practices within evidence-based literacy and aims at enhancing basic skills such as phonological awareness, decoding, and comprehension. This mixed-methods research employs a variety of tools, including assessments, surveys, interviews, and observations, in collecting both qualitative and quantitative data. The main focus of the study is to determine how much progress non-readers have made in their literacy development as a result of Project EL AR, which would ultimately serve as an informative source for educators, policymakers, and future studies related to reading difficulties.

Methodology

Research Design

A mixed-methods approach was used in this study. Both quantitative and qualitative methods. This study aimed to triangulate the findings from both quantitative and qualitative data sources, providing a more comprehensive and holistic understanding of the effectiveness of the Project EL AR pedagogical approach for selected non-reader learners in Grade 3. The combination of quantitative and qualitative methods allowed for more robust analysis and interpretation of the data, offering valuable insights into the student's reading progress, learning experiences, and the overall effectiveness of the approach.

Participants

The participants comprised selected non-reader learners in Grade 3 at LR Sebastian Elementary School. Non-reader learners were identified based on their performance in the pre-test assessment and demonstrated significant difficulties in reading.

Procedure

The researcher has undergone multiple steps to collect both quantitative and qualitative data from the selected non-reader learners in Grade 3 at LR Sebastian Elementary School. The researcher secured a written permit from the school principal. Then, the researcher also asked permission from the teachers and parents to be interviewed and explained the purpose of the study. To assess the students' reading abilities, a pre-test was administered using the Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (CRLA) tools, both in Filipino and English. Following the implementation of the Project EL AR pedagogical approach, the same CRLA test was administered as a MoSY assessment to measure any changes in the students' reading abilities. Classroom observations were conducted to gather qualitative data on the students' engagement, behavior, and interactions during Project EL AR activities.

Data Analysis

Quantitative data from the BoSY and MoSY assessments were analyzed using statistical techniques, such as descriptive statistics and inferential analysis, to determine the significance of any changes in the students' reading abilities. Qualitative data from observations, interviews, and student reflections were analyzed using thematic analysis to identify common themes and patterns related to the students' experiences and perceptions of the Project EL AR approach.

Table 1. CRLA Oral Reading Profile

Reading Profile	Score	Interpretation
Emergent	0-14	FR
Developing	15-20	MR
Transitioning	7-16	LR
Grade Ready	17-20	GR

The Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (CRLA) pre-test results reveal significant insights into the reading abilities of the students in both Filipino and English subjects. In Filipino, it appears that 66 students require a full refresher/ non-reader, suggesting significant gaps in their reading abilities. Meanwhile, 27 students need a moderate refresher, indicating some level of understanding but a need for further improvement.

A group of 43 students only need a light refresher, demonstrating a good grasp of reading in Filipino, but could benefit from some reinforcement. Impressively, a total of 126 students are grade-ready, showcasing strong reading abilities in Filipino and readiness for their grade level.

Turning to English, the data shows that 74 students require a full refresher, indicating substantial gaps in their reading skills. A smaller group of 36 students needs a moderate refresher, suggesting a certain level of understanding but a need for further enhancement. 60 students require a light refresher, indicating a good grasp of reading in English, but could use some reinforcement. In contrast to Filipino, fewer students, 92 in total, are grade-ready in English, indicating strong reading abilities and readiness for their grade level.

From this data, it can be inferred that a larger proportion of students are ready for grade-level reading in Filipino compared to English. This suggests that the Project EL AR approach may need to focus more on improving English reading skills among the students. However, it's also crucial to acknowledge that a significant number of students in both subjects require a full refresher/ non-reader, indicating a need for comprehensive interventions to enhance their reading abilities.

Ethical Considerations

This research study which examines how effective Project EL AR is on Grade 3 non-readers has several ethical issues that need to be considered. Informed consent from parents/guardians is needed as well as assent from the children themselves while paying attention to their appreciations since they play a role in this decision-making process.

Confidentiality and anonymity are preserved during research activities for future reference hence sensitive information is kept away thereby avoiding any possible danger. There should be an encouraging and friendly environment for intervention with minimal chances of causing psychological or social harm. Participant’s welfare should be a top priority to ensure fairness and justice in the selection and treatment of all concerned. Moreover, researchers must adhere to scientific rigor by providing precise and transparent findings while following ethical codes.

Results and Discussion

Level of pupils’ reading performance Before and After the Project EL AR

Table 2. Comparative number of pupils in pretest and posttest in terms of Full Refresher level

Subjects	BoSY		MoSY	
	Filipino	English	Filipino	English
Number of pupils tested	262	262	262	262
Full Refresher/ Non-Reader Level	66	74	0	35

Significant improvement in the pupils’ reading performance after the implementation of Project EL AR.

Test	Mean	T-Value	P-Value	Remarks
Pre (66 pupils)	3.96			
Post (20 pupils)	13.1	5.27	0.0001	Significant

The CRLA BoSY and MoSY results provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of the Project EL AR pedagogical approach.

In the Filipino subject, the BoSY results showed that 66 students required a full refresher, 27 required a moderate refresher, 43 required a light refresher, and 126 were grade ready. Remarkably, the BoSY results revealed that no students required a full refresher, suggesting a significant improvement in reading abilities. The number of students needing a moderate refresher more than doubled to 58, and those requiring a light refresher also increased to 82. The number of grade-ready students slightly decreased to 124.

Overall, these results indicate a substantial shift from students needing a full refresher to requiring only moderate or light refreshers, thus demonstrating the effectiveness of the Project EL AR approach in improving Filipino reading skills.

In English, the BoSY results indicated that 74 students required a full refresher, 36 needed a moderate refresher, 60 required a light refresher, and 92 were grade ready. The MoSY results showed a marked improvement, with the number of students requiring a full refresher reduced to 34. The number of students needing a moderate refresher more than doubled to 85, and the number requiring a light refresher slightly increased to 62. The count of grade ready students decreased slightly to 82. These results suggest that while there is a significant decrease in students requiring a full refresher, the number of grade-ready students remained relatively stable, indicating that further interventions might be needed to enhance English reading skills to the grade-ready level.

Conclusions

The research indicates that CRLA BoSY and MoSY provide strong evidence of the effectiveness of the Project EL AR pedagogical approach in improving reading abilities among students. The approach has successfully reduced the number of students requiring a non-reader, indicating significant progress in addressing reading gaps. However, further efforts may be needed to enhance the number of grade-ready students, particularly in the English subject. These findings highlight the importance of ongoing support and intervention to ensure that all students reach the desired grade-level reading abilities.

References

- Bataliran, J. M., Gaza, J. S., & Villasin, L. M. (2024). IMPROVING THE READING LEVEL OF GRADE VI GRAPPLING READERS THROUGH PROJECT SEL-P (Strategic Enhancement Learning-Package). *Ignatian International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(8), 1699-1718.
- Edra, L. (2023). Project Edra (Educational Video-Assisted Reading Activities): A Reading Intervention Tool to Improve The Reading Performance of Grade 1 Pupils at Catanauan Central School. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 12(1), 112-115.
- Niala, S. J. (2023). Project e-Localized: A Utilization of Electronic Books and Printed Localized Reading Materials to Enhance the Level of Reading Comprehension in Filipino of Grade Three. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 14(10), 1153-1157.
- Rodelyn, D. Y. (2024). ENHANCING THE READING ABILITY OF GRADE TWO TO SIX LEARNERS THROUGH PROJECT WISER IN A SELECT PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOL IN INFANTA DISTRICT. *Ignatian International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(2), 300-307.

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Jasmin Dumamba-Salilama, LPT, MAED
 LR Sebastian Elementary School
 Department of Education – Philippines